

An experimental study of fracture toughness for nano/ultra-fine grained Al5052/Cu multi-layered composite processed by accumulative roll bonding

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Abstract

In this study, ultra-fine grained Al5052/Cu multi-layered composite has been produced by accumulative roll bonding (ARB) and fracture properties have been studied using plane stress fracture toughness. The fracture toughness has been investigated for the unprocessed specimens, primary sandwich and first, 2nd and 3rd cycles of ARB process by ASTM E561 and compact tension specimens. Also, the microstructure and mechanical properties have been investigated using optical microscopy, scanning electron microscopy, uniaxial tensile tests, and microhardness measurements. The value of plane stress fracture toughness for the ultra-fine grained Al5052/Cu composite increased by increasing the number of ARB cycles, continuously from the primary sandwich to end of the 3rd cycle. The maximum value of 59.1 MPa.m^{1/2} has been obtained that it is about 2.77 and 4.05 more than Al5052 and pure Cu (unprocessed specimens). This phenomenon indicated that ARB process and the addition of copper to aluminum alloy could increase the value of fracture toughness to more than three times. The results showed that by increasing the ARB cycles, the thickness of copper layers reduced and after the 5th cycle, the excellent uniformity of Cu layers achieved. By increasing the number of ARB cycles, the microhardness of both aluminum and copper layers have been significantly increased. The tensile strength of the sandwich has been enhanced continually, and the maximum value of 566.5 MPa has been achieved.

Keywords: Ultra-fine grained Al5052/Cu Multi-layered composite; Accumulative roll bonding process; Fracture toughness; Mechanical properties; Microstructure.

1. Introduction

Multi-layered metal composite is consisting of several layers with different properties. Multi-layered composite has attracted interest from many designers due to its high strength-to-weight ratio. Al is used much more than other light alloys such as Mg and Ti to produce multi-layered composites due to the simultaneous presence of appropriate strength, ductility, and excellent corrosion resistance [1, 2]. It is known that the Al-Cu composites exhibit desirable properties of both copper and aluminum. So, low density, high ductility, excellent corrosion resistance, and high electric conductivity could simultaneously merge which make Al-Cu composites suitable for use in different industries of electrical, automotive, and aerospace [3, 4].

In the last decade, fabrication of bulk multi-layered composites by severe plastic deformation (SPD) processes has been considered and developed quickly because of some advantages of SPD over other means such as casting, deposition and powder metallurgy [5]. The accumulative roll bonding (ARB) is a type of SPD method suitable for processing sheet specimens introduced by Saito et al. in 1998 [6, 7]. In recent years, this method has been used as a novel approach for manufacturing of multilayered MMC composites [8]. The main advantageous of ARB process are the simplicity of the process, relatively accessible and inexpensive equipment, high production rate, and continuous production which increase its industrial capabilities. During the last years, though several metallic laminated composites, for example, Al/Ni [9], Al/Cu [10, 11], Al/Zn [12], Mg/Al [13] and Al/Cu/Ni [14] have been successfully processed using ARB method. However, almost no study has been done on producing Al alloy/Cu composites, especially Al5052/ Cu composite. The conclusions of the all of these research mainly proved that the ARB process is also able in the manufacturing of multilayered sheets from same or different materials [9, 13, 15]. The metal matrix composites showed improved mechanical properties and microstructure [8, 16]. A new production method such as ARB process, cannot be used in engineering structures and appliances unless a detailed understanding of their fracture properties is provided. There are some works in the fracture behavior of UFG materials that some of these studies reported fracture toughness reduction and increase after grain refinement of SPD methods. It has been reported that UFG nickel produced by high-pressure torsion process (HPT) and commercially pure titanium prepared by equal channel angular pressing (ECAP) after one pass, had lower fracture toughness compared to unprocessed specimens [17, 18]. Also, it has been reported that UFG pure Cu (processed by CGP) and Al 7075 (processed by ECAP) had higher fracture toughness compared

to unprocessed specimens [19, 20]. But so far no research has been done on multilayered composites. Also, no research has been done on materials that produced by ARB process. In this research, both subjects have been considered, the effect of the ARB process on the plane stress fracture toughness and plane stress fracture toughness for a nano-structure/ultra-fine grained multilayered composite.

In this study, Al5052 has been bonded to pure copper at the room temperature by ARB process, and an ultra-fine grained Al5052/Cu multilayered composite has been produced in the five cycles. Then, the microstructure and mechanical properties of the manufactured multi-layered composite have been evaluated after different ARB cycles. Also, the plane stress fracture toughness of ultra-fine grained multilayered Al5052/Cu composites has been investigated at the room temperature.

2. Experimental Procedure

2.1 Materials

Materials have been used in this study included 5052 aluminum alloy (Al bal., Mg 2.2, Fe 0.4, Cr 0.2, Si 0.2, Mn 0.1, Zn 0.1, Cu 0.1) and commercially pure copper sheets with unprocessed dimensions of 120 mm in length, 50 mm in width and 1 mm in thickness.

2.2 ARB Process

Fig. 1 demonstrates a schematic illustration of the ARB process in two steps. At first, a primary sandwich has been fabricated and then the accumulative roll bonding process has been carried out. To produce the primary sandwich, at first, two aluminum and copper sheets have been prepared at same dimensions. Then, these three sheets have been degreased in acetone, dried in the air, and have been scratch brushed and stacked on each other as shown in Fig. 1. Then, the sheets have been assembled as a sandwich stack included aluminum layers as the outer surfaces and one copper layer as the inner one. The stack has been clamped through copper wires at four edges to prevent slippage. Finally, to produce primary sandwich, a 60% reduction in thickness has been applied so that the thickness of sandwich stack reached 1.2 mm from 3 mm by rolling at room temperature. After the fabrication of the primary sandwich, the specimens have been cut in half and then surface treatment including degreasing with acetone, drying in the air, and roughing with a steel brush has been applied. Finally, the roll-bonded sheets with a 50% reduction in thickness value have been created. The ARB process repeated up to 5 cycles. The operation has been

performed using a laboratory rolling mill with 107 mm in roller diameters at room temperature in which no lubricant has been used.

2.3 Microstructure

The microstructures of unprocessed and processed specimens have been evaluated by optical microscopy. Samples after each cycle were cut using wire electro discharge machining in the parallel to the rolling direction. Then, they were grinding using sandpaper numbers 180 to 4000 and polishing by alumina powder with a size of 1 μ m and 3 μ m. Also, to evaluate the rupture mode, failure surfaces of the uniaxial tensile test specimens have been investigated through VEGA TESCAN scanning electron microscope.

2.4 Mechanical properties

Mechanical properties of ultra-fine grained Al/Cu composite prepared by the ARB process have been studied through uniaxial tensile tests and microhardness measurements. The uniaxial tensile test specimens have been made for the unprocessed and ARB processed sheets oriented along the rolling direction according to the ASTM E8/E8M-9 standard. The gauge length and width of the tensile test specimens were 6.92 and 2.5 mm, respectively. The uniaxial tensile tests have been performed at a nominal unprocessed strain rate of $1 \times 10^{-4} \text{ s}^{-1}$ at room temperature using SANTAM tensile testing machine. Also, the difference between gauge lengths before and after uniaxial tensile test defined the total elongation for each specimen. The Vickers microhardness tests have been done for unprocessed, and ARBed specimens using JENUS apparatus under a load of 200 gr applied for 10 s. Microhardness tests have been implemented to both aluminum and copper layers at ten different points randomly on the cross-sections perpendicular to the rolling direction. Then, for each copper and aluminum layers the minimum and maximum hardness were disregarded.

2.4. Plane stress fracture toughness

To assess fracture properties of unprocessed (5052 aluminum alloy and commercially pure copper), and ARBed specimens (primary sandwich, first, second and third pass) have been

prepared. Fracture tests have been done using at least three samples for each cycle to investigate the repeatability of the results. All of the fracture tests have been performed by displacement control at a constant rate. Samples have been loaded quasi-statically at a moving head speed of 0.05 mm/s up to the maximum load and beyond, until the full separation of the specimen. Compact tension specimen introduced by ASTM-E647 standard has been used. According to ASTM-E647 standard CT specimens have been prepared using a wire cutting machine. Pre-cracks have been made in the sample through wire-cutting technique. This pre-crack creation approach has been approved by Mourad [21]. The specimen size was 23.75 mm×22, 8 mm×1 mm thick, which is shown in Fig. 2. In the specimen, a narrow slit has been introduced by machining. It has been terminated into a 60° v-notch. The tip of the v-notch has been further extended up to 1 mm with $(\frac{a_0}{w})$ ratio equal to 0.40. This extension has been done through wire-cut machining with the wire radius of 200µm. It is to be noted that the CT type specimen was under purely Mode I loading condition. The experimental set-up of CT specimens and fixture are shown in Fig. 3.

3. Results and discussion

3.1 Microstructure

Fig. 4 illustrates the microstructure of ultra-fine grained Al5052/Cu multi-layered composite after the ARB process. Copper layers were continuous and coherent in an aluminum matrix at the end of the second cycle. There was almost no plastic instability approximately up to the second cycle. By increasing the number of ARB cycles from 3rd to 5th cycle, the plastic instability has been observed in copper layers. However, copper layers have been distributed in the continuous aluminum matrix. According to the conducted researches, the formation of plastic instability between dissimilar metals such as Al and Cu has been influenced by different mechanical properties of them, in which the harder layer (Cu) started necking and failure first [9, 11, 12, 22, 23]. Fig. 4 (f) demonstrates the microstructure of Al5052/Cu multi-layered composite after the ARB process through the fifth cycle. It could be seen that the copper and aluminum layers have been bonded together entirely and no separation at the interface has been seen. Though, plastic instability (i.e., necking) has been observed at none of the ARB cycles except in the fifth cycle. As is realized the value of the critical strain for fracture of the layers was high enough, which would be provided by the higher number of ARB passes. Fig. 5 demonstrates the thickness variations for copper layers at different passes of the ARBed Al5052/Cu composite. By increasing

the number of the ARB passes, the thickness of the copper layers decreased significantly due to the applied high strains. Finally, at the fifth pass, the minimum thickness of copper layers has been achieved. Also, the copper layers have been distributed uniformly along the aluminum matrix layer. As is known from the literature, the thickness reduction value to reinforce layers at the early ARB passes was more than that in the last ARB cycles in which layers have been experienced separation and distribution [24].

3.2 Mechanical properties

Fig. 6 illustrates the micro-hardness variation of copper and aluminum layers individually at various ARB passes. As shown, it is apparent that by increasing the number of the ARB passes, the microhardness of both layers (aluminum and copper) have been increased. The microhardness after the first step has been enhanced 1.3 and 2 times compared to the unprocessed specimens. Accordingly, the sharp rise in the microhardness at the early passes could be explained by work hardening or increasing the dislocations density and the subsequent formation of subgrain boundaries [11, 12, 14, 25, 26]. Increasing the number of ARB passes from the second to the fourth leads to increase in the value of microhardness of both aluminum and copper layers. Though, the rate of increase was less than early cycles. This may be because the work hardening and grain refinement are larger in early stages of SPD processing [27, 28]. At the intermediate passes, the rate of work hardening was less than the unprocessed passes [14, 29]. Finally, the microhardness reached a saturated value resulted from saturation in the grain size. At the last pass, the value of microhardness of aluminum and copper layers reached to 142HV and 169.6HV, respectively. By comparing them with the unprocessed specimens, the value of microhardness of aluminum and copper layers increased 1.55 and 2.27 times, respectively after the second step. The main reason for increasing microhardness was grain refinement [11, 12, 14, 25]. Also, the difference in thermal expansion coefficient between the matrix and reinforcement due to the heat caused by the friction of the rollers and the subsequent production of dislocations could be involved in increasing of microhardness [14, 30].

The stress–strain curves of the unprocessed specimens and multilayer composite Al5052/Cu after the ARB process through a different number of cycles are shown in Figs. 7 and 8. It is clear that by raising the number of the ARB cycles, the strength increases. The results were in good

agreement with the other research results on Al/Cu and Al/Cu/Ni composites processed by ARB [11, 14].

Fig. 9 represents the variation of tensile strength and elongation of the multilayer composite Al5052/Cu processed by ARB through different cycles. As shown, the tensile strength increased continuously up to fifth cycles. The maximum value of tensile strength has been achieved after the fifth cycle of ARB process and it reached 566.5 MPa. This strength value was 2 and 5 times higher than that of the unprocessed Al5052 and Copper sheets, respectively. However, the elongation of unprocessed and final sandwich remained almost unchanged. The trends of tensile strength and elongation were in good agreement with the results of the last investigations about the fabrication of multi-layered or metal matrix composite by ARB [11, 12, 14, 25]. Researchers reported that several major factors could influence the tensile strength of metal matrix composites with and without reinforcing. These factors were work hardening, grain refinement, shape, type and size of the particle, the amount of applied deformation, quality of bonding layers, and distribution of reinforcements [11, 12, 14, 25, 29-31].

At the early ARB passes, strengthening was mainly due to work hardening, the formation of low angle subgrain boundaries and increasing the density of dislocations according to Fig. 4(f) [11, 12, 14, 29]. Then, the mechanism of strengthening was mainly due to grain refinement so that at the last cycles of ARB process, the value of strength increased because of the fine-grained microstructure and the distribution of the copper reinforcements. By increasing the number of ARB passes from the second to the fifth, the quality of the connection layers improved due to the distribution of the reinforcing material, and also cracks were closed and crack propagation would be delayed.

Table 1 compared the strength and ductility of multilayered Al5052-Cu composite which has been processed in the present study with those from previous works. It could be realized from Table 1 the higher strength and ductility have been obtained from the current prepared UFG Al5052-Cu composite in comparison with those of earlier studies, including Al/Cu, Al/Cu/Al₂O₃, Al/Ni/Cu and Al/Cu/Mn composites which were processed by ARB. The strength of 566.5 MPa and ductility of 9.61% have been achieved, which were about 47% and 21 % greater than the maximum values obtained in the literature. This means that using 5052 Al alloy instead of pure Al is recommended for processing of Al/Cu multilayered metallic composites with or without particulate

reinforcements. Also, plastic instability and fracture of copper layers took place at the early stages of ARB processed pure Al/Cu composites while they took place in the final stages of ARB prepared Al5052/Cu composites. Different strain hardening behavior has been seen in the processed Al5052/Cu composite in comparison with the processed pure Al/Cu composite because Al 5052 alloy had lower stacking fault energy than pure Al.

3.3 Fractography

Fig. 10 illustrates the tensile fractured surfaces of Al and Cu sheets after the uniaxial tensile testing. The primary fracture mechanism of the most coarse-grained metals with FCC crystal structure is a ductile fracture. Ductile fracture appears slowly after plastic deformation and necking with the creation of small dimples and coalescence to each other and ultimate failure [32].

Fig. 11 shows tensile fractured surfaces of Al5052/Cu multi-layered composite at Al and Cu layers after primary sandwich. As shown, the ductile fracture mode with the formation and coalescence of dimples has been seen in both cases. SEM micrographs of tensile fractured surfaces of Al5052/Cu multi-layered composite produced via multipass ARB are presented in Fig. 12. It has been reported that early ARB cycles exhibited lower bonding between the layers compared to the last cycles. Also, there was a lamellar structure between matrixes and reinforcing that disappeared by the increasing number of ARB cycles [30]. For this reason, micro cracks may nucleate at the interfaces between matrix and reinforcement which caused failure [11, 14, 30]. By increasing the ARB cycles, bonding between copper and aluminum layers was stronger, though still lamellar structure has been considered after the fifth cycle according to Figs. 12a-12f. It could also be seen that the fractured surfaces of Al and Cu layers at the primary sandwich exhibited ductile mode and composed of coaxial dimples. The ductile fracture has been occurred in the materials having a low dislocation density and at grain boundaries with hemispherical and gray holes. By increasing the number of the ARB cycles in comparison with an unprocessed sandwich, the depth and size of dimples decreased, and finally, stretched dimples formed and fracture mechanism changed from ductile to shear ductile mode (see Fig. 12 (f)). These results have been confirmed by the previous work results [11, 14, 22].

3.3. Plane stress fracture toughness

The load-CMOD (Crack Mouth Opening Displacement) and R-curves for the unprocessed (Al5052 and pure Cu) and multilayered Al5052/Cu composite after the third pass of ARB process are presented in Fig. 13. The maximum load and R-curve of the specimens (Pmax) could be calculated with these pictures. Table 2 contrasts the maximum load and fracture toughness of the multilayered Al5052-Cu composite specimens and unprocessed specimens (Pmax). According to the results of Table 2, It could be realized that by increasing the number of ARB cycles, the value of maximum load increased and the higher Pmax has been obtained from the ARB processed Al5052-Cu composite in the third pass. According to Table 2, maximum load of specimens has been affected by strength and its rate of change was quite similar in tensile strength.

The experimental plane stress fracture toughness of the specimens (K_C), could be obtained by ASTM E-561. It should be noted that, the value of K_C for different samples must be specified at the instability condition from the tangency between the R-curve and the applied K-curve of the specimens. Also, using ASTM-E8M, for the CT specimens, the crack grows resistance (K_r), can be computed as follows:

$$k_{r_i} = \frac{p_i}{b\sqrt{w}} \times f_i \left(\frac{a}{w} \right) \quad (I)$$

$$f_i \left(\frac{a}{w} \right) = \left[\frac{2 + \frac{a}{w}}{\left(1 - \frac{a}{w}\right)^{\frac{3}{2}}} \right] \left[0.886 + 4.64 \left(\frac{a}{w} \right) - 13.32 \left(\frac{a}{w} \right)^2 + 14.72 \left(\frac{a}{w} \right)^3 - 5.6 \left(\frac{a}{w} \right)^4 \right] \quad (II)$$

Where, (Pmax), (w), (B) and (a) were the maximum applied load, specimen width (19mm), specimen thickness (1.5mm) and crack size (7.6mm), respectively and it was valid for $\frac{a_0}{w} \geq 0.35$. The coefficient $f_i \left(\frac{a}{w} \right)$, which only depended on the specimen geometry and based on the standard, the given expression for $f_i \left(\frac{a}{w} \right)$ was considered. Fig. 14 demonstrates the failed specimens after the fracture test. It is shown that the crack grew straightly in the direction of crack front for all specimens which was a witness of symmetry and pure mode I (opening mode) loading. Plane stress fracture toughness of each pass was determined using Eq (I). Considering the material and geometry conditions, the computed maximum load and fracture toughness were within the valid range indicated by the standard. Figs. 15 shows the R-curved for a primary sandwich, first, second

and third pass of ARB process. Also, Table 2 and Fig.16 show the value of plane stress fracture toughness of specimens before and at the different ARB cycles. According to these results, the fracture toughness increased for the primary sandwich in comparison to unprocessed specimens (Al5052 and pure Cu) and reached to $39.8 \text{ MPam}^{1/2}$ and it was 1.87 and 2.73 higher than Al5052 and pure Cu. This was due to increase in strength and cold work after primary sandwich. For the next ARB passes, fracture toughness increased continuously and the maximum value reached in 59.1 that was obtained in the third pass, and it was 2.77 and 4.05 higher than Al5052 and pure Cu, respectively. Trends for the plane stress fracture toughness was similar to the variation of tensile strength that by increasing the number of ARB cycle the rate of increase for strength and fracture toughness reduced. Strength and ductility are the two major factors that affected the value of fracture toughness. After a primary sandwich, ductility changed with a low rate, so that it could be considered a constant and tensile strength increased. Thus, with increasing tensile strength, fracture toughness increased. As mentioned in the present results and in the similar investigations, after a remarkable reduction in ductility of the material for the first ARB passes, the ductility increased with the very low rate. So, the trend of increase in the fracture toughness was similar in strength so that after the first pass increased sharply and then with low rate improved. This trend for Cu CGPed specimens also occurred but for ECAPed specimens the value of fracture toughness decreased after the first cycle and then increased [17, 18, 20]. On the other side, in the UFG materials higher grain boundaries volume fraction, crack tip blunting and crack arrest played a much more important role in fracture resistance which resulted in fracture toughness enhancement [20]. Furthermore, as the grain size decreased, some mechanisms such as grain boundary accommodation, grain boundary triple junction activity, grain nucleation and grain rotation were intensifying [20]. Since these mechanisms control rates of the plastic energy released at the nanoscale, it was expected that fracture toughness increased after grain refinement [33]. Some experimental works on metallic materials proved that the hardening region such as a plastic zone was enlarged after grain refinement [34-36]. This fact could also be assumed as one of the reasons for fracture resistance enhancement observed in UFG materials. On the other side, uniformity and homogeneity of microstructure in crack growth were also the impressive parameters. As mentioned in the microstructure evaluation, by increasing the ARB pass, microstructure became more homogeneous and more appropriate bond at the interfaces to be created.

Two basic mechanisms were responsible for changes in mechanical properties during the ARB process such as strain hardening by dislocations and grain refinement [29, 37-39]. Increasing the value of strength in the initial cycles of the ARB process, related by strain hardening and cold work as the important role. [39-42]. After initial cycles, the effect of work hardening decreased and strengthening and higher strengths have been achieved by the gradual evolution of microstructure and grain refinement. Results of mechanical properties of this study were in good agreement with these mechanisms. So both mechanisms in the ARB process could be increased the fracture toughness by the main reasons.

4. Conclusions

In the present study, the ultra-fine grained Al5052/Cu multi-layered composite has been generated through the ARB process up to 5 cycles, and the plane stress fracture toughness, mechanical properties and microstructure were investigated and the results have been concluded as follows:

- Copper reinforcement layers were continuous along the aluminum matrix, and there was almost no plastic instability at early cycles.
- By increasing the number of ARB cycle to the 5th cycle, the plastic instability (necking and fracture) has been observed at copper layers, and multi-layered composite with uniform Cu distribution has been fabricated.
- The thickness of copper layers was 1000 μm at the unprocessed specimen. It has been reduced to $\sim 7 \mu\text{m}$ after the 5th cycle of ARB cycle.
- By increasing the number of ARB cycles, the microhardness of both aluminum and copper layers has been increased.
- The tensile strength of the sandwich has been enhanced continuously. The higher strength of 566.5 MPa and ductility of 9.61% have been achieved which were about 47% and 21 % greater than the maximum values resulted in the literature.
- By increasing the number of ARB cycles, the plane stress fracture toughness enhanced, continually and the 3rd pass reached to 59.1 $\text{MPa}\cdot\text{m}^{1/2}$ that was 2.77 and 4.05 higher than Al5052 and pure copper as the unprocessed specimens, respectively.

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- Investigation of the tensile fracture surfaces during the ARB process, indicated by increasing the number of the ARB passes, the fracture mechanism changed to shear ductile fracture.

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Table 1. Comparison of strength and ductility of the multilayered composite obtained in this study with those from previous works.

Materials	Reference	Maximum value of El (%)	Maximum value of UTS (MPa)
Al5052-Cu	This study	9.61	566.5
Al-Cu	[11]	7.93	365
Al-Cu	[10]	7.3	ab
Al-Cu-Al ₂ O ₃	[30]	5	361
Al-Ni-Cu	[14]	7.8	346
Al-Cu-Mn	[29]	6.9	355

Table 2: Variation of P_{max} and fracture toughness for unprocessed and ARBed specimens

Number of ARB cycles	Tensile strength (MPa)	Elongation (%)	P_{max} (N)	K_c (MPa.m ^{1/2})
Al 5052	273.6	21.9	537	21.3
pure copper	167.4	39.7	369	14.6
sandwich	414.5	8.9	941	39.8
pass 1	499.1	8.6	1038	49.9
pass 2	519.9	8.4	1070	55.3
pass 3	532.6	9.1	1104	59.1

Figure 1. Schematic illustration of ARB for processing ultra-fine grained Al5052/Cu multilayered composite.

Figure 2: CT test specimen geometry according to ASTM E647 and typically prepared specimen for the first cycle of ARB process.

Figure 3: (a) Experimental set-up with celestron microscopy for crack growth measurement and (b) CT test specimen with fixture under loading.

Figure 4. The microstructure of ARB processed Al5052/Cu multi-layered composite (a) primary sandwich and after (b) first cycle, (c) second cycles (d) third cycles, (e) fifth cycles (f) Fracturing and necking of copper layers after five ARB cycles.

Figure 5. Thickness variations of copper layers at different cycles of ARB processed Al5052/Cu composite.

Figure 6. Microhardness variation of copper and aluminum layers individually at different cycles of ARB processing of Al5052/Cu composite.

Figure 7. The stress-strain curves of unprocessed specimens.

Figure 8. The stress-strain curves of ARB processed Al5052/Cu composite.

Figure 9. Variations of the tensile strength and elongation of Al5052/Cu composite processed during different cycles of ARB.

Figure 10. Tensile fractured surfaces of unprocessed sheets before ARB process.

Figure 11. Tensile fractured surfaces of Al5052/Cu multi-layered composite: (a) Al layer after primary sandwich (b) Cu layer after primary sandwich.

Figure 12. Tensile fracture surfaces of Al5052/Cu multi-layered composite: (a) primary sandwich and after (b) first cycle, (c) second cycles (d) third cycles, (e) fourth cycles and (f) fifth cycles.

Figure 13: Typical load-CMOD curves in the CT tests of the unprocessed and primary sandwich.

Figure 14: ARBed specimens after fracture toughness test.

Figure 15: R curve for different ARBed specimens: (a) primary sandwich, (b) first cycle, (c) second cycle and (d) third cycle.

Figure 16: Variation of fracture toughness for unprocessed and ARBed specimens.

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Figure 1

Figure 2

Figure 3

Figure 4

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Figure 11

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Figure 12

Figure 13

Figure 14

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Figure 15

Figure 16

